

GAN-based data augmentation for crack detection

Alberto Botana López*, Daniel Gordo Martín,
Adrián Alonso Rial, Jacobo Otero Tranchero
and Santiago Muñoz-Landín*

Technological Centre AIMEN, C/ Relva, 27 A. Torneiros - 36410 Porriño - Pontevedra, Spain

*alberto.botana, santiago.muinos@aimen.es

Abstract—The application of Machine Learning for manufacturing has become a reality with the ongoing digitalization of factories. Generative Models are a promising but not yet exploited enough technology in manufacturing frameworks. In this work, we apply Generative Models for a quality inspection problem in order to generate synthetic data for training. We show how through the use of a Generative Adversarial Network, synthetic images are generated to augment the training data set of a crack detection system. We show the impact of such data generation in the detection ratios of our system and how for problems with inhomogeneous defect typologies distribution, Generative Models can provide a solution for artificial defect generation to enhance detection capabilities based on neural networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

Manufacturing Frameworks are a perfect scenario for the deployment of Machine Learning (ML) techniques [1], the validation of their applicability and also the incubation of new algorithms and ideas. The huge amount of data that comes out from different widely sensorized manufacturing frameworks and its current digitalization has triggered the evolution of several technologies towards the autonomy, adaptability and self-organization of devices deployed along factories all around the world. However, one bottleneck for the efficient application of some ML techniques that rely in the use of Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) is the large amount of data required for training. In particular, many Quality Inspection procedures are based in Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) [2] for image processing that need large amount of images for it. This, added to the obvious fact that in general factories try to minimize the existence of defects, makes that having large amounts of images of defects tends to be difficult. In addition, defects usually appear in a way that can be classified by some common features meaning that different defect typologies can be identified for the same process and the frequency at which the different typologies appear is usually different. Which means that examples of some defect typology can be massively acquired and examples of some other can be rarely seen. The impact of this, makes that a quality control procedure might show really good results for some typology while remaining almost blind for the detection of another.

In this work we take as initial point a CNN-based crack detection system developed in previous own work. Such system detects cracks from metallic parts within a manufacturing

framework in the automotion sector. The detection is based on the non-destructive use of magnetic nanoparticles [3] to highlight the regions where cracks appear. The defects of our scenario are distributed in different typologies and detection ratios are quite different depending on them. We use a generative approach to generate synthetic image data for training of our CNN with a significant impact on the detection ratios. This section gives a short overview of the non-destructive testing technique used in our context and also of the state of the art Generative approach followed for our purpose. The next section introduces the problem and the different elements involved in its solution which is explained in the third section of this paper. Finally results are shown and commented and conclusions are exposed with a description of future work triggered by the presented development.

A. Non-Destructive Testing Method: Magnetic Particles

The automation of crack detection, has been topic of different developments within last years [4] in order to achieve similar or higher accuracy compared with traditional methods while making at the same time jobs more attractive for workers. Until now, this method, when based on the use of magnetic particles [5], consisted on a factory worker spending full working days inspecting these metallic pieces under black light looking for clusterings of these kind of fluorescent particles. This technique, known as *magnetic particle inspection* [6] belongs to the so called non-destructive testing techniques [7]. In this case, by magnetizing a ferromagnetic material by direct or indirect magnetization and applying a coat of ferrous particles mixed with fluorescent dye, these particles result attracted towards the cracks or corrosion pits on the surface, since these defects create a flux leakage field in the magnetized material. These clustered particles can then be easily seen when shone upon with black light, since it interacts with the fluorescent dye making it shine on a bright green color (see Fig.1).

B. Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN)

Generative Adversarial Networks, or GANs are a class of machine learning frameworks designed by Goodfellow et al. [8] in 2014. GANs have been used extensively for a wide range of tasks such as creating faces [9], domain-changing

Fig. 1. Magnetic field inside a ferromagnetic material with a crack. On top of it rests a high concentration of magnetic particles (blue volume). The zoom of the image shows one example of the cracks detected in our case by the accumulation of these particles (bright green line) showing fluorescence response under the application of UV light.

image-to-image translation [10] and even video synthesis [11]. These models consist of two separate sub-models: A *generator* that tries to come up with new images from a dataset, and a *discriminator* that, having access to the training database, tries to differentiate an original picture from the database from a picture created by the model’s generator. These two sub-models compete with each other in the form of a zero-sum game.

In this training process, the generator will start by generating random noise in a latent space, which will be transformed into an image by running it through several transposed convolution layers which will upscale the image according to its weights up to a fixed size. Once that has been done, the discriminator, by running the generator output through a series of convolutional layers, will try to guess whether the image produced was indeed forged by the generator or it belongs to the real dataset. This way, the objective of the generator is to maximize the error rate of the discriminator by effectively fooling it, since that means that its outputs are so good that they can’t be distinguished from the real data. In order for both of the sub-models to be trained properly, independent backpropagation is applied to both parts. A schematic diagram representing this process can be found on Fig. 2.

II. PROBLEM

For the problem addressed in this work, we analyzed metallic parts in the production line and prototypes of a factory in the automation sector. The main source of defects in these pieces is the appearance of cracks. A crack is defined as a thin, irregular line over the surface of a piece that is the beginning of a future breakage. Therefore, their early detection becomes critical. They are produced by over-heating or variations in the process parameters during the fabrication. The manufacturing method is based on batch production, where items with similar characteristics are produced in the same production run. We developed a clustering algorithm based on *TSNE* [12] and *K-Means* [13] [14] that helped us to identify up to 6 different classes of crack based on its morphology and location within the piece. An example for every crack type can be found on Fig. 3. The main problem we addressed and where this work is focused, was to achieve similar detection rates for all the defect

Fig. 2. Schematic rundown of a GAN training process. Two Networks, Generator and Discriminator (both in orange), in a game theory context using real data to generate synthetic images.

typologies, given that such asymmetry in the defect typology distribution and specially the low number of examples for some typologies, made the accuracy of the detection procedure poor some certain typologies while being high for others. To automate the crack detection process we developed an image acquisition system to take images from the piece to inspect and a neural network responsible for classification. A detailed definition of this detection system is out of the scope of this work, although we will remark some details in next sections.

A. Detection Setup and Dataset

To create the dataset, a custom setup was designed to take images of the pieces. It was formed by two fixed cameras, an ultraviolet light lamp and an industrial claw. The two cameras were the model acA2000-50gc [15] from Basler, which are industrial cameras that can deliver up to 50 frames per second at a maximum of 2 MP resolution. The process was the following: one of the faulty pieces was placed in the claw and it rotates every second from 20 to 30 degrees according to the size of the piece. In the moment the piece was motionless, the two cameras took an image from different angles. So we were able to obtain between 12 and 16 images for every piece. These images were stored in HDF5 [16] files for its subsequent labelling. For manual labelling an interface was programmed

Fig. 3. Examples of each of the six crack types identified by clustering. The typology depends on the form of the crack but also on its position within the piece analysed.

using python. The information flow of this data acquisition process can be seen in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Information flow of the detector system. The cracks from the pieces are digitalized taking images from them. All the images are included in a dataset in HDF5 format where they are manually labelled. The GAN uses real images for training to generate synthetic ones that are included in the dataset to train the detection model.

For industrial companies the cost to serve nonconformities is very high, so defects tend to be a rare event, in the order of PPM (parts per million). Therefore, the dataset we worked on was characterized by the low number of cracks examples available. We also found problematic the lack of homogeneity in the classes distribution, so our detector performed better for the majority class than for the rest. We can see the class distribution in Fig. 5. Furthermore, defective pieces from the same production batch tend to be quite similar, as they have suffered the same production conditions, so many of their cracks did not add additional variety to the dataset.

Fig. 5. Cracks type distribution. The different frequencies at which different typologies of defects are detected results in a highly asymmetric dataset where some typologies can only be poorly trained for detection.

B. Detection Network

The detection method we used was based on a fully convolutional network (FCN) [17]. We chose a ResNet50 [18] network with pre-trained weights as a feature extractor. The last fully connected layer of this network was removed and replaced by a block formed by two consecutive layers:

- Average pooling layer with a pool size 7×7 and stride 1.
- Convolutional 1×1 with stride of 1 and zero padding.

Thus, the ResNet50 outputs a feature map, showing the spatial location of features in the image. This volume is fed to the new block which outputs a segmentation map. Finally, this segmentation map is overlapped to the whole image and region of interest are extracted with skimage measure module [19]. Some details of the experimentation process:

- **Optimization** We used SGD with a learning rate of 10^{-3} , a momentum of 0.9 and a weight decay of $5 \cdot 10^{-4}$. We noticed that this method outperformed other optimizers for this problem, as it had a faster convergence. We did not freeze any layer as we got a better performance training the whole network.
- **Patch-sampling** In a first stage of the project, background samples were chosen at random. In a later stage, we used trained models to select the most interesting background regions and include them in the training.
- **Augmentation** To increase the size of the training set we applied random data augmentations during training. The transformation applied were shear mapping, image zooming, horizontal and vertical shift, brightness, rotation and flipping.

III. PROPOSED SOLUTION

The proposed solution to fix this lack of training data was to use **FastGAN**, a minimal and lightweight GAN proposed by Liu et al. [20]. This proposed model was centered around the

Fig. 6. Schematic of the FastGAN generator architecture.

premise of being able to produce high fidelity results without high-end equipment, training only for a few hours on a single NVIDIA RTX-2080 GPU unit. The architecture of this model can be seen on Fig. 6 and 7, both reproduced from the original authors in [20].

A. Generator

In order to be able to generate high-fidelity results, the generator needs a lot of up-sampling layers, since each of these will effectively double the resolution of the output. However, a deeper model with more convolution layers will end in a higher computational cost and a longer training time. To overcome this, He et. al [18] designed the residual block structure, which connects the layers using a skip-layer connection, which link two layers further than one block apart, effectively skipping one or more layers and thus boosting the gradient signal. This method, however, while decreasing the raw amount of time required, it does increase its computational cost.

To compensate for this complexity increase, the authors reformulated this skip-layer idea, coming up with the Skip-Layer Extraction (SLE) module. This module firstly implements skip-connection as an channel-wise multiplication of the activation layers from different convolutional layers. This differs from the ResBlock, as in that method implements skip-connection as an element-wise addition instead of the multiplication. In addition, they use a different approach regarding the sample resolution of the skip-connections. Previous authors only used skip-connections when dealing with the same resolution, while the authors perform skip-connections between resolutions with a much broader range, like 8^2 and 128^2 . This is possible since, by implementing the skip-connections as a multiplication instead of an addition, the spatial resolution is no longer needed. These two main advantages allow for a much simpler computation, affording both in complexity and training time.

B. Discriminator

In order to provide the discriminator with a strong regularization, it was treated as an encoder as a whole and trained it with small decoders, forcing the discriminator to extract image features. These decoders are optimized along with the discriminator using a reconstruction loss following:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{recons}} = \mathbb{E}_{f \sim D_{\text{encode}}(x), x \sim I_{\text{real}}} [||\mathcal{G}(f) - \mathcal{T}(x)||] \quad (1)$$

Where f is the intermediate feature-maps from the discriminator, the \mathcal{G} function contains the processing on f and \mathcal{T} represents the processing on sample x from real images I_{real} .

This discriminator model, shown in Fig. 7 employs encoders on only two scales: f_1 on 16^2 and f_2 on 8^2 , along with only four convolution layers in order to produce images with a resolution of 128×128 pixels. By acting this way, the computational cost of the regularization is reduced by much more than other regularization methods. In order to obtain the final image, f_1 is cropped with $\frac{1}{8}$ of its original size, then the real image is cropped by the same amount, thus obtaining I_{part} . Then the decoders produce I'_{part} from the firstly cropped f_1 and I' from f_2 . Lastly, the discriminator and decoders are trained together to minimize the loss depicted on equation 1 by trying to match I' to I and I'_{part} to I_{part} .

Taking this reconstructive approach allows the discriminator to obtain a more comprehensive representation from the inputs, since it's able to cover the big picture through f_2 as well as the finer details through f_1 .

IV. RESULTS

After training the model for 150 epochs, it was prompted to generate a batch of 3000 images. Some of those generated images can be seen on Fig. 8. On most cases, the produced result mimic the original images successfully, although there are some examples, like those shown on figure 9 which don't represent any kind of crack contained within the original

Fig. 7. Schematic of the FastGAN discriminator architecture.

Fig. 8. Examples of Generated images outputted by the model for each of the six different crack typologies. The GAN managed to generate images even for those typologies that were clearly minority.

dataset. These images, as is often common when training GANs, represent complete nonsense while trying to keep a familiar style with the dataset. These faulty examples will be taken care of in future models by implementing a reinforced model to this GAN architecture, effectively building an Object-Reinforced Generative Adversarial Model, or ORGAN [21]. This generated data was added to our train set and a new detection model was trained. We compared the new detector performance with other detection model, using the same architecture, to which these images were not added to the training set. Both models were trained using the same parameters, some of them were defined above. The test set consisted in 239 pieces from various production batches never seen by the system before in order to avoid any bias. Every piece is represented by between 12 and 16 images. The test set had 118 defective pieces and 121 non-defective ones. A defective piece was considered to be correctly classified if we detect, at least, a crack in one of the images. Finally, the metric selected

Fig. 9. Flawed images generated by the model. The figure shows examples of some images that appear within the synthetic dataset and need to be manually filtered.

for comparison was f1-score. Thus, the model trained with synthetic data was able to classify correctly the 95.7% of the defective pieces and the f1-score metric was 0.83, meanwhile the model trained without the synthetic data classified correctly the 90% of defective pieces and the f1-score was 0.79.

A. Future Steps

Our main purpose in order to perfect this model is to enhance this architecture and turn it into an ORGAN, so that it can be fine tuned and give access to more control over the crack generation process. This way, the faulty crack generation problem would be mostly nonexistent and we would be able to produce a specific type of crack according to the model's needs. Additionally, in order to increase model accuracy, a bigger crack dataset will be used on further model trainings.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, an application of Generative Adversarial Models has been proposed in order to produce synthetic data to increase the size of a dataset and, thus, improve the performance of a FCN-based detector. We have shown that GAN generated synthetic data can be a useful tool for problems where we have to deal with small datasets. We consider this method can complement and overcome the limitations of traditional data augmentation techniques which only focus on 2D transformations.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work has been developed within the frame of the Joint Research Unit “F4ctorIA” between GKN Driveline Vigo and AIMEN Technology Centre, granted by the Galician Innovation Agency and co-funded by the European Union through the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) with reference IN853A-2020/02. Operational Program FEDER GALICIA 2014-2020. AB, DG and SM want to thank the fruitful comments and discussions of all the members of the Artificial Intelligence and Data Analytics Lab at the Smart Systems and Smart Manufacturing Department of the AIMEN Technology Centre.

REFERENCES

- [1] Z. Kang, C. Catal, and B. Tekinerdogan, “Machine learning applications in production lines: A systematic literature review,” *Computers Industrial Engineering*, vol. 149, p. 106773, 2020.
- [2] A. Dhillon and G. Verma, “Convolutional neural network: a review of models, methodologies and applications to object detection,” *Prog Artif Intell*, vol. 9, p. 85–112, 2020.
- [3] P. Prabhu Gaunkar, D. C. Jiles, and G. V. Prabhu Gaunkar, “Detection of surface cracks in ferromagnetic materials by c-scan mapping of residual stresses using barkhausen emissions,” *AIP Advances*, vol. 10, p. 015246, 2020.
- [4] W. Zhang, Z. Zhang, D. Qi, and Y. Liu, “Automatic crack detection and classification method for subway tunnel safety monitoring,” *Sensors*, vol. 14, pp. 19307–19328, 2014.
- [5] A. P. Mouritz, “Introduction to aerospace materials. nondestructive inspection and structural health monitoring of aerospace materials,” *Woodhead Publishing*, vol. 10, pp. 534–557, 2012.
- [6] H. Lester, “Magnetic particle inspection,” in *Symposium on Magnetic Particle Testing*. ASTM International, 1945.
- [7] M. MR Jolly, A. Prabhakar, B. Sturzu, K. Hollstein, R. Singh, S. Thomas, P. Foote, and A. Shaw, “Review of non-destructive testing (ndt) techniques and their applicability to thick walled composites,” *Procedia CIRP*, vol. 38, pp. 129–136, 2015.
- [8] I. J. Goodfellow, J. Pouget-Abadie, M. Mirza, B. Xu, D. Warde-Farley, S. Ozair, A. Courville, and Y. Bengio, “Generative adversarial networks,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1406.2661*, 2014.
- [9] S. . A. T. Karras, T. and Laine, “A style-based generator architecture for generative adversarial networks,” *In arXiv preprint arXiv:1812.04948*, p. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1812.04948>, 2019.
- [10] J. A. Grant-Jacob, B. S. Mackay, B. J. A. G., Y. Xie, and M. Heath, D. J. and Loxham, “A neural lens for super-resolution biological imaging,” *Journal of Physics Communications*, vol. 3, no. 6, p. 065004, 2019.
- [11] T.-C. Wang, M.-Y. Liu, J.-Y. Zhu, G. Liu, J. Tao, A. and Kautz, and B. Catanzaro, “A neural lens for super-resolution biological imaging.”
- [12] L. van der Maaten and G. Hinton, “Visualizing data using t-SNE,” *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, vol. 9, pp. 2579–2605, 2008. [Online]. Available: <http://www.jmlr.org/papers/v9/vandermaaten08a.html>
- [13] H. Steinhaus, “Sur la division des corps matériels en parties,” *Bull. Acad. Polon. Sci*, vol. 1, no. 804, p. 801, 1956.
- [14] S. Lloyd, “Least squares quantization in pcm,” *IEEE transactions on information theory*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 129–137, 1982.
- [15] Basler AG. (2021) Basler ace aca2000-50gc. [Online]. Available: <https://www.baslerweb.com/en/products/cameras/area-scan-cameras/ace/aca2000-50gc/>
- [16] The HDF Group. (2000-2010) Hierarchical data format version 5. [Online]. Available: <http://www.hdfgroup.org/HDF5>
- [17] T. D. Jonathan Long, Evan Shelhamer, “Fully convolutional networks for semantic segmentation,” *arXiv:1411.4038*, 2014.
- [18] K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, and J. Sun, “Deep residual learning for image recognition,” in *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, 2016, pp. 770–778.
- [19] S. Van der Walt, J. L. Schönberger, J. Nunez-Iglesias, F. Boulogne, J. D. Warner, N. Yager, E. Gouillart, and T. Yu, “scikit-image: image processing in python,” *PeerJ*, vol. 2, p. e453, 2014.
- [20] B. Liu, Y. Zhu, K. Song, and A. Elgammal, “Towards faster and stabilized {gan} training for high-fidelity few-shot image synthesis,” in *International Conference on Learning Representations*, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://openreview.net/forum?id=1Fqg133qRaI>
- [21] G. L. Guimaraes, B. Sanchez-Lengeling, C. Outeiral, P. L. C. Farias, and A. Aspuru-Guzik, “Objective-reinforced generative adversarial networks (organ) for sequence generation models,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1705.10843*, 2017.